

ALMA 2030 and beyond: front end technology improvement

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Improve ALMA front-end and system

Options to improve ALMA systems

- Improve instantaneous RF bandwidth
 - Increases sensitivity in full band integration
 - **No penalty for spectral line observation should result**
 - Frequency mapping speed
- Improve noise temperature of receiver/mixer
 - Are receivers atmosphere limited?
 - Are receivers quantum limited?
 - Calibration accuracy
- Improve Sky Mapping speed
 - Focal plane arrays
 - **Ultimately large single dish**
- Improve flexibility of the system

Instantaneous RF bandwidth

- Initial remark: just doubling receiver RF coverage does not lead to increase of instantaneous bandwidth → No sensitivity improvement!
- **Evolutionary:** increase IF bandwidth
 - 4 GHz per SB channel -> 8 per SB channel, i.e. 4-20 GHz, or 0-20 GHz (current plan)
 - Requires an upgrade of correlator (planned) and (currently) an upgrade of all receivers
- **Evolutionary:** double down conversion system
 - Requires only dynamic range improvement (ENOB) in correlator
 - Receiver system change
- **Systematically:** true simultaneous dual/multiple band system
 - ALMA band 6/7, ALMA band 6/9, ALMA band 6/7/9
- **Ultimately, beyond 2030: frequency array**
 - All/most sky transmission windows bandwidth is available to correlator for processing

Doubling RF coverage

Planned **ALMA band 2** cartridge covers ALMA band 2 and ALMA band 3, but currently not instantaneous bandwidth. Since it is a HEMT amplifier system, it can be potentially fitted by dual down converter, allowing true dual band operation

Requirements:

- Compact WCA downconverter
- Upgradable/modular IF switch, distribution
- Upgradable Digital transport
- Upgradable Correlator

Double down conversion

A main mixer in the system can be followed up by second cryogenic mixer at high frequency, which in turns will produce 4-12 GHz frequency output.

Remarks:

- In SSB scheme, does not need increasing of digitizer band and with current 5 ENOB, there may be enough dynamic range in the correlator
- The second mixer is working at low frequency thus it is expected to have low noise and high gain, alleviating in parts requirements of IF amplifier noise, i.e. making for possibility of compromise for a wider band system
- An up/down conversion scheme (Kojima et al) can be also employed as second mixer

Dual frequency ALMA B6/9 example

Benefits:

- Improved phase calibration, continuous phase transfer without losing array area, or obs. time, **ngEHT plan is dual/triple band!**
- Enabling the highest resolution imaging with ALMA
- Observation of transient phenomena
- High redshift resolved cosmic star formation history
- **Limited changes in ALMA system**

Dual/multiple band

- Quasi-optical combination (up to two bands)
- HEMT driven ultra wideband cartridge (multiplexing) see ALMA band 2 example
- On cartridge dual/triple band system (higher integration)
- Combination of quasi-optical, in cartridge for >2 bands at once

Requirements:

- Compact WCA downconverter
- Upgradable/modular IF switch, distribution
- Upgradable Digital transport
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TW Hydraye

Large FOV of low frequency band can be combined with smaller FOV for high frequency band for a hotter, more compact zone around 1 au
Mach sharper image would be possible than with B9 alone, and wider FOV of B6 would add information

Frequency Array Receiver >2030

Quasi-optical system

An on-chip system

Key advantages

- Continuous phase transfer
- All atomic/molecular lines are available in one go in high resolution
- Much more information is available for atmospheric transmission correction
- Possibility to study large spectral features (dust)
- Possibility to exclude atmospheric line forest – background limited total power performance
- Blind red shifted CII, CO, CI search (SUPERSPEC, DESHIMA science)
- Ultimate ALMA/ATLAST front-end backend
- **Remark: Clearly observed development direction for total band coverage (SMA)**

Sensitivity, are we quantum noise limited?

Significant Improvement On Trec are possible

From ALMA DFWG report

Improving sideband ratio

**DSB->2SB
upgrade gives
large
improvement**

**B9-SEPIA
Hesper et al**

From ALMA DFWG report

Attacking quantum limit $hf/(2k)$

Mixer physical temperature?

- In many SIS mixer bands receiver noise temperature decreases if bath temperature decreases
 - 4K -> 2K change is approx. 30% decrease in T_{rec} in ALMA band 9
 - What if 4K -> 0.8K?
 - **0.8 K is available by fitting an inexpensive He4 sorption cooler to existing system**
 - Also needed by parametric amplifiers
 - **Needs study in the laboratory**

Focal plane arrays

- Addressed in many talks (see Realini et al)
- It will likely require change of front-end design, which should come after 2030 if ALMA is to be improved significantly
- Needs similar correlator/transport resources as frequency arrays
- For large spatial multiplexing and medium spatial resolution --- **Large single dish (ATLAST)**

Focal Plane array (multiband)

2x2 array beam footprint for dual frequency system, blue low frequency, red high frequency

Phased array feed (PAF) configuration can be adopted for low frequency while at the same time high frequency array can be 2f lambda spaced array

The transition from PAF mode to discrete mode needs to be studied

PAF mode can be achieved in correlator post processing as phas and amplitude is preserved

Conclusions

- While improving IF bandwidth, there is a limit, which can be overcome by doing more IF channels in parallel, i.e. multiple band receivers, which would be the next logical step beyond 2030
- Sensitivity of SIS mixers can be improved further in various ways, ALMA is receiver sensitivity limited
- While upgrading, care should be taken to consider modularity (in IF system and correlator) to enable future improvements
- For focal plane/ frequency arrays, a decision will need to be taken in the future (>2030) when ALMA main front end system needs a total redesign. We need to start addressing/preparing for that now